

DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN NATIONAL GROUPS ON THE BASIS OF THE WORKS OF A.S. PUSHKIN

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Annotation: This article discusses the issues of how Pushkin's works influence the oral speech of students in national groups. Pushkin as a whole era of the Russian people.

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Pushkin's language is distinguished by novelty in terms of the volume of lexical means, the breadth of coverage of various language units. The idea of rapprochement of folk colloquial speech with literary book became the main principle not only of Pushkin's literary activity, but also of the development of the national literary language as a whole.

The struggle for nationality, for the united is the upholding of its national basis. Pushkin abandoned the severe restrictions on the use of common language means that were imposed by the Karamzinists. Pushkin saw in the "common dialect" the basis of the literary language. Pushkin constantly refers to the language of the common people, sees in it "a picturesque way of expression." In the language of the people, in their songs, proverbs and fairy tales, Pushkin discovered many speech nuggets. He sensitively listened to folk songs, finding "true poetry" in them. The poet treated the words and expressions of the common people with attention and respect. He constantly showed a keen interest in them, admired their accuracy and imagery.

Pushkin contrasted the rich and figurative speech of the people with the closed, poor and limited jargon of the "high society". Pushkin got acquainted with his native language from various written sources. In his library were and had traces of various notes collections of epics, songs, proverbs. The folklorists could not distinguish the songs written by him from the folk ones. In the Pskov province, he wrote down a whole notebook (about 50) of folk songs. He made extracts from collections of proverbs and gave interpretations to them. By 1824, Pushkin's first recordings of folk songs and the first attempts at artistic adaptation of folk poetry belong.

Pushkin showed interest in dialects, advised to listen to common people's sayings. It includes many vernacular words and expressions and syntactic constructions in literary usage. From year to year, his attention to colloquial speech increased, colloquial and colloquial elements were increasingly introduced into the language of works of art. If during the lyceum period Pushkin only occasionally used them,

then the first work where the means of folk speech are used freely and boldly both in the speech of the characters and in the speech of the author was the poem "Ruslan and Lyudmila" (1820), met with criticism unfriendly. Critics were outraged by the abundance of "low" words and expressions, the hero's transition from one manner of speech to another, the mixing of genres - the use of elegiac phrases in a fairy tale.

Pushkin boldly breaks the boundaries of genre speech styles, creating new types of literary works. He broke the forced connection between genre and language style. He created "romantic" and historical poems ("Ruslan and Lyudmila", "Poltava"), a novel in verse ("Eugene Onegin"), a poetic story ("Count Nulin"). In all these new works, he freely uses elements of the three previous literary styles. His one work could include a wide variety of speech elements. Pushkin focuses not on the laws of the poetics of classicism, but on the expediency of use. Colloquial and common folk elements were involved in book speech even before Pushkin, but their choice and purpose were different. In the XVIII century. they were included in the literary speech as a means of naturalization, stylization. However, organic merging into a single literary speech did not occur. Only Krylov in the fable genre, and Griboedov in the comedy genre, achieved a harmonious combination of elements of book and colloquial speech.

Pushkin, on the other hand, achieved an organic fusion of the common people and the bookish language into a single literary speech in all genres and types of fiction. In Pushkin's works, elements of colloquial speech are no longer a sign of their genre affiliation, but a property of the Russian national literary language. The sphere of folk vernacular in Pushkin's works has been significantly expanding since the mid-1820s, from the time of his stay in Mikhailovsky. Living in the countryside, Pushkin hourly communicated with serfs, guslars, beggars, listened to their songs, fairy tales, conversations, wrote down fairy tales, legends, epics, proverbs and sayings. Dressed in a red Russian shirt, he appeared at fairs and rural bazaars, jostling among the crowd and participating in popular amusements. During these years, his main interlocutor was the nanny Arina Rodionovna, from whose words he wrote down numerous fairy tales.

Pushkin makes extensive use of colloquial vocabulary in such works as "Peter the Great's Moor", "Gypsies", "Poltava", "Eugene Onegin", "The Bronze Horseman", "Belkin's Tales", "Boris Godunov", "The Captain's Daughter", "Queen of Spades", "Dubrovsky".

For example, in "Boris Godunov": drink a cup for a tavern, damned, sons of bitches; in "The Tale of the Fisherman and the Fish": fool, dupe. The vocabulary of Pushkin's fairy tales contains a significant admixture of vernacular, as well as

numerous stylistic devices, proverbs and formulas of folk poetry. Literary rights are acquired by many popular colloquial words and expressions: poor fellow, poor man, riot, shrill, rumble, ruffle, climb, crumple, out of spite, tipsy, importunate, bother, dirty, interpret.

Functions of using folk colloquial vocabulary and phraseology in Pushkin's work:

1. Pushkin makes extensive use of everyday vocabulary of folk speech to describe the typical features of Russian life in the village: cabbage soup, stove, broom, tub, pots, poker, tongs, pancakes, round dance, kvass, swings, firewood, barn, splinter, irradiation, sheepskin coat, sleigh, hut, caftan, hut, bed. This is a stylistic function of using folk colloquial vocabulary in order to create national and local color. Now we perceive such words as lexemes with a cultural-historical component, since they, while retaining a subject-material meaning, a nominative function, simultaneously characterize the everyday culture of a century, a country, or any of its regions.

2. Pushkin uses vernacular and vernacular words to create a speech characterization of a hero of a certain social position - a soldier, a peasant, a coachman.

3. In works stylized as folklore, Pushkin uses the words, forms and artistic and visual means of UNT (lexicon with emotionally expressive suffixes, the use of postpositive particles, the infinitive with the suffix "-ti", repetition of prepositions, syntactic parallelism in negative comparison).

4. Vernacular also penetrates into the author's speech: the lyrical hero is emphatically sincerely talking with the reader.

5. Low, familiar vocabulary is used in epigrams, polemical attacks.

Colloquial, colloquial words and expressions in Pushkin's language are subjected to strict qualitative and quantitative selection in accordance with the principle of proportionality and conformity. "True taste does not consist in the unconscious rejection of such and such a word, such and such a turn, but in a sense of proportion and conformity," wrote Pushkin.

Pushkin was more careful and more moderate in his use of colloquial and common folk means than the authors of the 18th century, especially the authors of comedies and fables. Pushkin avoids everything that is incomprehensible and unknown in the general literary and everyday life. He is alien to the exotic regional expressions, did not allow rude vernacular, jargon. Pushkin's language hardly uses the professional and class dialects of the city, and eschews the colloquial bureaucratic dialect. Only in some works do we find individual words and expressions determined by the content of the texts, for example, in The Queen of

Spades - the words and expressions of gamblers, in *The House in Kolomna* - military terms.

Pushkin from vernacular takes only common, generally understood words that can receive national recognition: # maybe, poor man, out of spite, promise, climb, immediately, bake .

The selection of words and expressions from folk speech is subject in Pushkin's work to the principle of proportionality and conformity. He deliberately selects the most striking elements from folk speech, using them in different contexts, with different goals, preliminarily processing the means of the folk language.

Pushkin selects from the folk language into the literary language such speech means that have been historically tested, i.e. widely used in chronicles, songs, legends, epics and therefore known to all the people. The poet did not use local dialect words. He conducted the selection in urban vernacular and peasant everyday speech, and not in the jargon of secular salons. Pushkin did not allow a large number of roughly colloquial, dialectal and slang words. He did not stoop to a naturalistic fixation of dialect speaking.

Pushkin finds original features in folk usage that characterize its genuineness and originality. For example, in the poem "The Drowned Man" dialectisms are used mistress ("wife, eldest woman in a peasant family"), weather ("bad weather, storm"); in "The Captain's Daughter" - "an inn, or, in the local way, is smart . " Pushkin makes a strict, careful selection of vocabulary and uses dialectal features in special stylistic tasks: to create a character of documentary, reliable accuracy.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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